

01/07/2025

FHERITALE

Newsletter 02

Update from Project Co-ordination

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Since our last update to you in March, project partners have been collaborating across multiple work packages in our pursuit of the FHERITALE objectives. Read on for a refresher on the aims of the project, key events in our first reporting period, as well as more recent updates, including newly submitted deliverables and Milestones. As ever we welcome all with an interest in the impact artificial materials are having on our food, health, and the environment to reach out with comments and ideas - your input is always welcomed!

OVERVIEW OF THE FHERITALE CONSORTIUM

This newsletter:

UPDATE FROM FHERITALE COORDINATORS

PAGE 01

KEY EVENTS IN RP1 + LANDSCAPE OF SERVICES

PAGE 02

PUBLICATIONS AND PRESENTATIONS OF PROJECTS RESULTS

PAGE 03

RECENT OUTPUTS AND WHAT'S NEXT

PAGE 04

KEY EVENTS IN RP1

FHERITALE kicked off in 2024, and there have been many notable updates from the project so far. Check out our timeline highlighting a selection of key events and outputs from the project so far.

Literature search

05/08/2024

Partners at CERM/CIRMMP conducted extensive analysis of literature surrounding Micro and Nanoplastics, Bioplastics, Plastic Additives, and Metals/Metal Oxides, to illustrate current and future research prospects.

Utrecht strategic meeting

14/10/2024

Alongside invited experts, project partners met in Utrecht to update on progress so far and provide input into current challenges and priorities for researchers in this field

FHERITALE White paper

15/04/25

A white paper highlighting the selected priorities of the project, as well as challenges and recommendations that have emerged in the project thus far

FHERITALE KOM

16/01/2024

Project partners met in Florence, Italy, to kick off the project, introduce the partners, and establish effective working patterns.

Survey disseminated

27/08/2024

A questionnaire to understand the services available through European RIs to researchers seeking to understand the impact of artificial materials on food, health, and the environment. Assembled by UU, and shared through relevant channels by partners.

Survey results shared

02/04/2025

Results of the survey were shared for wider community. Resources across 8 different RIs/ESFRI landmarks were highlighted as being relevant to researchers within the remit of the FHERITALE project

A CROSS-THEMATIC LANDSCAPE OF AVAILABLE SERVICES

The FHERITALE Consortium identified a large variety of services that can be accessed through European Research Infrastructures.

These services range all the way from omics techniques to cell culture facilities and to biophysical analysis.

Access an overview of the identified services through this QR code

Want to add a service provided by your facility or RI?
Contact pheritale@instruct-eric.org

Service Type	Number of available services in this category	Research Infrastructures offering this service
Physical/chemical characterisation of Microplastics or other Microparticles	37	AnaEE-ERIC, EIRENE-RI, EMBRC-ERIC, EuroBioImaging-ERIC, Instruct-ERIC, METROFOOD-RI, MIRRI-ERIC
Physical/chemical characterisation of Nanoplastics or other Nanoparticles	31	AnaEE-ERIC, EIRENE-RI, EMBRC-ERIC, EuroBioImaging-ERIC, Instruct-ERIC, METROFOOD-RI, MIRRI-ERIC
Physical/chemical characterisation of Micro/Nanoparticles based on origin: Artificial, Natural, or Engineered	20	AnaEE-ERIC, EIRENE-RI, EMBRC-ERIC, EuroBioImaging-ERIC, Instruct-ERIC, METROFOOD-RI, MIRRI-ERIC
Structural characterisation of Microplastics + other microparticles	27	AnaEE-ERIC, EMBRC-ERIC, EuroBioImaging-ERIC, Instruct-ERIC
Structural characterisation of Nanoplastics + other Nanoparticles	22	AnaEE-ERIC, EMBRC-ERIC, EuroBioImaging-ERIC, Instruct-ERIC
Bioplastics (biodegradable vs bio-based)	17	AnaEE-ERIC, EIRENE-RI, EMBRC-ERIC, EuroBioImaging-ERIC, METROFOOD-RI, MIRRI-ERIC
Risk assessment of Micro/Nano particles	14	EIRENE-RI, EMBRC-ERIC, METROFOOD-RI, MIRRI-ERIC, ELIXIR
Exposure assessment of Micro/Nano particles	18	EIRENE-RI, EMBRC-ERIC, METROFOOD-RI, MIRRI-ERIC, ELIXIR
Toxicity of Micro/Nano particles	24	EIRENE-RI, EMBRC-ERIC, EuroBioImaging-ERIC, Instruct-ERIC, METROFOOD-RI, MIRRI-ERIC
Biological activity of Micro/Nano particles	24	EIRENE-RI, EMBRC-ERIC, EuroBioImaging-ERIC, Instruct-ERIC, METROFOOD-RI, MIRRI-ERIC
Monitoring of Micro/Nano particles	20	AnaEE-ERIC, EIRENE-RI, EMBRC-ERIC, EuroBioImaging-ERIC, Instruct-ERIC, METROFOOD-RI, MIRRI-ERIC

- AnaEE-ERIC
- Instruct-ERIC
- EIRENE-RI
- METROFOOD-RI
- EMBRC-ERIC
- MIRRI-ERIC
- EuroBioImaging-ERIC
- ELIXIR

PUBLICATIONS AND PRESENTATIONS OF PROJECT RESULTS

Engaging stakeholders and the scientific community is a pivotal objective of FHERITALE.

Recently, thanks to the valuable input of external experts and the continued collaboration among project partners, FHERITALE published its first articles on ORE (Open Research Europe). Additional publications on Zenodo, along with active participation in conferences and events, have helped link FHERITALE with broader scientific communities in a growing network of exchange, dialogue and new perspectives.

Bibliometric analysis of current research landscape

Murgioni, E., et al. (2025). From Environment to Health: A One Health Landscape of Research on Selected Artificial Materials. <https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.20244.1>

White paper: Key selected priorities

Boer, M. et al. (2025). Micro and Nanoparticles Research: Priorities, Challenges and Recommendations. Zenodo <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15222316>

Categorization of services and technologies

Mustatea, G., et al. (2025). FHERITALE - Categorization of Services and Technologies. Zenodo <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15554666>

Presentations and Talks at In-Person Events

Project partners presented FHERITALE at several events, offering an overview and inviting further interest through talks, posters, and follow-up discussions, including the most recent plastic workshop in Ravenna and the Instruct-NL Symposium

D5.1: CATEGORISATION OF SERVICES AND TECHNOLOGIES

Building on mapping of existing technologies (WP3) and enabling selected priorities (WP4), this deliverable seeks to categorise existing and emerging technologies the defined Service Readiness Classification (SRC).

Maturity of RI technologies and services is assessed by grouping into 3 distinct services

- **Category A:** High impact, fully operational services and technologies ready for immediate deployment
 - **Category B:** Technically functional technologies requiring adaptation to align with project goals
 - **Category C:** Technologies at early development or prototype stage, indicating an unmet need that must be addressed before they can be utilised.
- Category C serves to indicate gaps in RI landscape, and a need for targeted funding to support emerging technologies.

Read the full deliverable [here](#)

MS7: LIST OF TECHNOLOGY NEEDS AND THEIR TECHNOLOGY READINESS

To identify urgent technology needs within the community a combination of systematic literature review and AI-supported extraction tools were employed.

The milestone consolidates diverse technological needs emerging from both unmet research needs and policy recommendations. Key priorities identified across both EU projects and scientific literature are the detection and characterisation of nanoplastics, and generation of standards and reference materials. MS7 helps lay the foundation for creating a roadmap for future service development within FHERITALE, and will feed in to activities in other WP's.

WHAT TO EXPECT NEXT?

Webinars:

- FHERITALE webinars are due to begin again in September. Follow our social media accounts to stay updated!

Outputs

- FHERITALE outputs are shared by our social media accounts and posted on our website. New updates coming soon!

Zenodo

- You can also track our outputs on Zenodo via the dedicated [FHERITALE workspace](#)

Upcoming meetings

- Partners are meeting in Bucharest in October to discuss methods of gap analysis and thematic clustering.

Find out more about FHERITALE via our [website](#), and keep up to date with news via our social media channels

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